

Apparent molar volumes and viscosities of solutions of mono- and disaccharides in water and acetonitrile + water mixed solvent systems at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K

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Abstract Apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) and viscosities (η) of solutions of some mono- and disaccharides viz glucose, fructose, sucrose and maltose have been determined in water and in acetonitrile (AN) + water mixed solvent systems (10%, 20% and 30% v/v) at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K as a function of molar concentration. The apparent molar volume and viscosity data have been analysed in the light of Masson's and Jones-Dole equations respectively. The activation thermodynamic quantities ($\Delta\mu_1^{OH}$, $\Delta\mu_2^{OH}$, ΔH_2^{OH} and ΔS_2^{OH}) of viscous flow for mono- and disaccharides in water and in (AN + water) mixed solvent systems have been calculated at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K. The results in regard to solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions in purely aqueous and (AN + water) mixed-solvent systems have been discussed in terms of the values of constants of Masson's and Jones-Dole equations as well as in terms of activation thermodynamic quantities.

Keywords Apparent molar volumes, viscosities, mono- and disaccharides, mixed solvents

In continuation of our work¹ relating to viscometric and thermodynamic studies of interactions in ternary solutions containing maltose and sucrose in aqueous alkali metal halides at different temperatures, we now report the results of our studies on the apparent molar volumes and viscosities of solutions of mono- and disaccharides in purely aqueous and acetonitrile (AN) + water mixed solvent systems at different temperatures viz 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K. The results have been analysed and discussed in the frame work of solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions on the basis of the parameters of Masson's and Jones-Dole equations² as well as on the basis of thermodynamic activation parameters². Hydration of sugars is a topic of considerable importance and in this regard spectroscopic and volumetric studies by Franks³ and Suggett⁴ on the hydration of mono-saccharides have invoked the concept of solvent structure compatibility to explain the observed differences in solution behaviour of polyhydroxy molecules which differ only in the positions and orientations of potential hydration sites.

The present study has been undertaken in the light of the following aspects

(i) Determination of apparent molar volume (V_ϕ) from density data as a function of molar concentration of solu-

tions of glucose, fructose, sucrose and maltose in water and also in (AN + water) mixed solvent systems (10%, 20% and 30% v/v) at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K, (ii) Determination of limiting apparent molar volume (V_ϕ^0) of glucose, fructose, sucrose and maltose in purely aqueous solutions as well as in (AN + water) mixed solvent systems at different temperatures, (iii) Determination of partial molar volumes of transfer (V_{2tr}^0) of glucose, fructose, sucrose and maltose from water to (AN + water) mixed solvent systems at different temperatures, (iv) Determination of viscosities of solutions of glucose, fructose, sucrose and maltose in water and in (AN + water) mixed solvent systems at different temperatures, and subsequent analysis of viscosity data in the light of Jones Dole equation, and (v) Determination of free energies of activation of viscous flow, $\Delta\mu_1^{OH}$ and $\Delta\mu_2^{OH}$ per mole of solvent and solute respectively, at different temperatures and subsequent calculation of entropy (ΔS_2^{OH}) and enthalpy (ΔH_2^{OH}) of activation of viscous flow at different temperatures.

Results and discussion

The apparent molar volume (V_ϕ) in respect of solutions of mono- and disaccharides in water and in (AN + water)

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Table 1. Values of limiting apparent molar volume (V_{ϕ}^0) and experimental slope (S_v) for solutions of mono- and disaccharides in water and in (AN + water) mixed solvent systems at different temperatures

Mono- and disaccharides	V_{ϕ}^0 (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)				S_v (cm ³ dm ^{3/2} mol ^{-3/2})			
	Water	10% AN	20% AN	30% AN	Water	10% AN	20% AN	30% AN
	Temp. 293.15 K							
Glucose	112.34	192.45	202.54	212.53	-26.54	-42.06	-52.96	-62.89
Fructose	111.18	191.34	201.60	211.21	-23.09	-33.77	-43.02	-52.11
Sucrose	212.04	222.33	232.03	242.85	-47.12	-51.45	-61.27	-71.83
Maltose	229.75	239.67	249.55	259.41	-57.57	-60.73	-70.54	-80.08
	Temp. 303.15 K							
Glucose	113.34	193.85	203.84	213.95	-30.57	-43.09	-53.70	-63.49
Fructose	112.29	192.87	202.39	212.98	-27.83	-34.23	-44.82	-54.48
Sucrose	213.59	223.67	233.91	243.69	-49.09	-52.52	-62.20	-72.20
Maltose	230.62	240.41	250.51	260.42	-58.54	-61.06	-71.97	-81.49
	Temp. 313.15 K							
Glucose	114.89	194.11	204.29	214.35	-34.38	-44.47	-54.33	-64.18
Fructose	113.53	193.17	203.63	213.60	-31.30	-35.26	-45.59	-55.53
Sucrose	214.57	224.62	234.20	244.80	-51.26	-53.30	-63.30	-73.65
Maltose	231.15	241.79	251.42	261.14	-59.93	-62.79	-72.36	-82.59

mixed solvent systems of compositions 10%, 20% and 30% acetonitrile (v/v), as a function of molar concentration has been determined at three temperatures viz. 293.15, 303.15, 313.15 K using the following equation :

$$V_{\phi} = \frac{1000}{C \rho_0} (\rho_0 - \rho) + \frac{M}{\rho_0} \quad (1)$$

where the symbols have their usual significance.

The plots of V_{ϕ} versus $\sqrt{C}$ are linear in each case. This linear variation of V_{ϕ} with $\sqrt{C}$ is in keeping with the Masson's equation

$$V_{\phi} = V_{\phi}^0 + S_v \sqrt{C} \quad (2)$$

where V_{ϕ}^0 is the limiting apparent molar volume and is equal to the partial molar volume at infinite dilution (V_2^0) of the solute and S_v is the experimental slope.

The values of V_{ϕ}^0 and S_v determined by the method of least squares, in respect of the solutions of glucose, fructose, sucrose and maltose in water and in (AN + water) mixed solvent systems have been presented in Table 1. It is seen that the values of V_{ϕ}^0 are largely positive in water and in (AN + water) mixed solvent systems at different temperatures, which indicate the presence of strong solute-solvent interactions⁵. Further, on comparing the values of V_{ϕ}^0 in pure solvent (water) with those in presence of (AN + water) mixed solvent systems, it is found that there occurs an increase in V_{ϕ}^0 on going from 10% to 30% AN in (AN + water) mixed solvents thereby indicating increasing trend of solute-solvent interaction. This, in turn supports the behaviour of S_v which predicts decreased solute-solute interactions as the content of AN in the solutions increases

from 10% to 30% as shown by the decreasing values of S_v . Thus, on the basis of the values of V_{ϕ}^0 and S_v in purely aqueous solutions and those obtained in the presence of (AN + water) mixed solvent systems, it may be concluded that the molecules of mono- and disaccharides become more solvated in (AN + water) mixed solvent systems as compared to in pure water resulting in increased solute-solvent and decreased solute-solute interactions. A perusal of Table 1 shows that with rise of the temperature the values of V_{ϕ}^0 tend to increase while those of S_v tend to decrease. From this it follows that solute-solvent interactions tend to become stronger while those of solute-solute tend to become weaker with the rise of temperature.

Table 2. Partial molar volumes of transfer, ($\Delta V_{2,lr}^0$) for solutions of mono- and disaccharides from water to (AN + water) mixed solvent systems at different temperatures

Mono- and disaccharides	$\Delta V_{2,lr}^0$ (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)		
	10% AN	20% AN	30% AN
	Temp. 293.15 K		
Glucose	80.11	90.20	100.19
Fructose	80.16	90.42	100.03
Sucrose	10.29	19.99	30.81
Maltose	9.92	19.80	29.66
	Temp. 303.15 K		
Glucose	80.51	90.50	100.61
Fructose	80.58	90.10	100.69
Sucrose	10.08	20.32	30.10
Maltose	9.79	19.89	29.82
	Temp. 313.15 K		
Glucose	79.22	89.40	99.46
Fructose	79.64	90.10	100.07
Sucrose	10.05	19.63	30.23
Maltose	10.64	20.27	29.99

Table 3. Values of coefficients *A* and *B* of Jones-Dole equation for solutions of mono- and disaccharides in water and in (AN + water) mixed solvent systems at different temperatures

Mono- and disaccharides	<i>A</i> (dm ³ mol ^{-1/2})				<i>B</i> (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)			
	Water	10% AN	20% AN	30% AN	Water	10% AN	20% AN	30% AN
	Temp 293 15 K							
Glucose	-0.298	-0.367	-0.703	-0.9243	0.6167	1.1634	1.2722	1.5245
Fructose	-0.216	-0.609	-0.719	-0.8476	1.1675	1.2169	1.3326	1.5042
Sucrose	-1.232	-3.277	-3.614	-3.7295	3.7467	4.8052	5.2549	5.9486
Maltose	-1.315	-3.353	-3.706	-3.8315	4.0769	4.9105	5.3773	6.0867
	Temp 303 15 K							
Glucose	-0.326	-0.502	-0.838	-0.967	0.8372	1.1715	1.2780	1.5276
Fructose	-0.217	-0.652	-0.770	-0.907	1.2320	1.2596	1.4195	1.7275
Sucrose	-1.245	-3.590	-3.963	-4.005	4.0650	5.6794	5.6957	6.1326
Maltose	-1.436	-3.725	-4.053	-4.121	5.2527	5.8479	5.8200	6.2872
	Temp 313 15 K							
Glucose	-0.368	-0.616	-0.852	-1.084	0.952	1.184	1.578	1.534
Fructose	-0.263	-0.703	-0.787	-0.928	1.245	1.446	1.562	1.874
Sucrose	-1.392	-3.860	-4.056	-4.069	4.750	6.694	6.029	6.538
Maltose	1.714	-3.933	-4.150	-4.169	6.589	6.821	6.158	6.680

Partial molar volumes of transfer ($\Delta V_{2,tr}^0$) for the solutions of glucose, fructose, sucrose and maltose from water to (AN + water) mixed solvent systems have been obtained as below :

$$\Delta V_{2,tr}^0 = V_2^0(\text{AN + water}) - V_2^0(\text{water}) \quad (3)$$

The values of $\Delta V_{2,tr}^0$ thus obtained have been presented in Table 2. It is seen that in each case the values of $\Delta V_{2,tr}^0$ are positive and tend to become larger with the increasing percentage of AN in (AN + water) mixed solvent systems. This may be attributed to the decrease in electrostriction in the presence of acetonitrile⁶. Thus, the electrostriction effect which brings about the shrinkage in the volume of solvent is decreased in (AN + water) mixed solvent systems as compared with that in pure water. From the values of $\Delta V_{2,tr}^0$ it may also be inferred that the solvation of mono- and disaccharides increases with the increase in the content of acetonitrile thereby reducing the strong⁷ solvent-solvent interactions i.e. between acetonitrile and water.

Table 4. Free energy of activation for viscous flow, $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ for water and (AN + water) mixed solvent systems at different temperatures

Solvents	$\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)		
	293 15 K	303 15 K	313 15 K
Water	20.58	20.71	20.88
10% AN + Water	20.48	20.59	20.80
20% AN + Water	20.63	20.83	21.06
30% AN + Water	20.80	21.04	21.35

Viscosities of solutions of mono- and disaccharides in water and in (AN + water) mixed solvent systems have been determined at different temperatures as a function of molar concentration (*C*) and the viscosity data have been analysed in the light of Jones-Dole equation

$$\eta/\eta_0 = \eta_{rel} = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC \quad (4)$$

$$\text{or } \frac{(\eta_{rel} - 1)}{\sqrt{C}} = A + B\sqrt{C} \quad (5)$$

From the linear plots of $(\eta_{rel} - 1)/\sqrt{C}$ versus $\sqrt{C}$ (Fig. 1), the values of coefficients *A* and *B* have been determined by the method of least squares and the results have been presented in Table 3. It is seen that in each case the values of *A* are negative in water as well as in (AN + water) mixed solvent systems which indicate the presence of weak solute-solute

Table 5. Free energy of activation for viscous flow, $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ for solutions of mono- and disaccharides in water and in (AN + water) mixed solvent systems at different temperatures

Solvents	$\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)		
	293 15 K	303 15 K	313 15 K
	Glucose		
Water	116.63	150.65	171.28
10% AN + Water	195.36	206.57	223.81
20% AN + Water	190.29	196.54	238.38
30% AN + Water	179.52	192.68	235.46
	Fructose		
Water	190.89	205.51	213.22
10% AN + Water	194.96	206.35	236.50
20% AN + Water	197.23	213.35	236.28
30% AN + Water	203.58	234.61	257.55
	Sucrose		
Water	552.95	614.40	730.37
10% AN + Water	485.50	569.05	589.39
20% AN + Water	482.84	537.12	582.38
30% AN + Water	558.84	581.70	633.09
	Maltose		
Water	582.96	782.27	996.65
10% AN + Water	369.45	392.38	439.18
20% AN + Water	474.36	490.77	513.95
30% AN + Water	540.33	582.41	601.45

Table 6. Entropy of activation and enthalpy of activation of viscous flow for solutions of mono- and disaccharides in water and in (AN + water) mixed solvent systems at different temperatures

Solvent ^a ,	$T\Delta S_2^{0\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)			$\Delta H_2^{0\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)		
	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
	Glucose					
Water	297.28	312.57	333.54	413.91	358.60	383.29
10% AN + Water	-417.03	-431.25	-445.48	-221.67	-224.68	-221.67
20% AN + Water	-704.86	-728.91	-752.95	-514.57	-532.37	-514.57
30% AN + Water	-820.02	-847.99	-875.96	-640.50	-655.31	-640.50
	Fructose					
Water	127.83	134.41	143.43	318.72	180.43	193.18
10% AN + Water	-676.90	-629.67	-650.44	-413.94	-423.32	-413.94
20% AN + Water	-572.42	-591.94	-611.47	-375.19	-378.59	-375.19
30% AN + Water	-791.01	-817.99	-844.97	-587.42	-583.38	-587.42
	Sucrose					
Water	537.03	564.67	602.54	1089.99	610.69	652.29
10% AN + Water	-1522.64	-1574.58	-1626.52	-1037.14	-1005.53	-1037.14
20% AN + Water	-1459.09	-1508.86	-1558.63	-976.25	-971.74	-976.25
30% AN + Water	-1088.33	-1125.46	-1162.58	-529.49	-543.76	-529.49
	Maltose					
Water	1742.03	1831.67	1954.51	5842.81	2324.99	1877.69
10% AN + Water	-1022.14	-1057.00	-1091.87	-652.69	-664.62	-652.69
20% AN + Water	-580.28	-600.08	-619.87	-105.92	-109.31	-105.92
30% AN + Water	-895.83	-926.39	-956.95	-355.51	-343.98	-355.51

Fig. 1. Variation of $(\eta_{rel} - 1)\sqrt{C}$ with $\sqrt{C}$ for aqueous solutions of glucose at different temperatures; (□) 293.15 K, (Δ) 303.15 K, (O) 313.15 K.

interactions. On the other hand, the values of B are largely positive which suggest the presence of strong solute-solvent interactions. Further, the values of B are rendered more positive in the presence of (AN + water) mixed solvent systems as compared to those in pure water. This may be ascribed to the increased solute-solvent interactions in (AN + water) mixed solvent systems. Further, the positive values of B for mono- and disaccharides in water and in (AN + water) mixed solvent systems indicate that mono- and disaccharides behave as structure makers in these solvents⁸.

It would not be out of place to mention here the fact that Krikwood-Buff theory has been applied in the field of aqueous solutions and in hydrophobic interactions⁹. Recently, Zolkiewski¹⁰ has applied Krikwood-Buff integrals to study the nature of interactions in aqueous solutions of Caffeine.

Free energies of activation of viscous flow, $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ and $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$, per mole of solvent and solute respectively were calculated as below :

The coefficient B of the Jones-Dole equation is related to the free energy of activation by the following equation¹¹

$$B = \frac{\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0}{1000} + \frac{\bar{V}_1^0}{1000} [(\Delta\mu_2^{0\#} - \Delta\mu_1^{0\#})/RT] \quad (6)$$

where $\bar{V}_1^0$ and $\bar{V}_2^0$ are the partial molar volumes of the solvent and solute respectively. $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ is the free energy of activation per mole of pure solvent and $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ is the free energy of activation per mole of solute. The values of $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ and $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$

therefore those of $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ were calculated using the following equations¹²

$$\Delta\mu_1^{0\#} = RT \ln (\eta_0 \bar{V}_1^0 / hN) \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta\mu_2^{0\#} = \Delta\mu_1^{0\#} + \frac{RT}{V_1^0} [1000 B - (\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0)] \quad (8)$$

where R , h and N are gas constant, Planck constant and Avogadro's number respectively; and T is the absolute temperature.

The entropy of activation ($\Delta S_2^{0\#}$) for different mono- and disaccharides has been calculated from the following relation¹¹

$$\frac{d(\Delta\mu_2^{0\#})}{dT} = -\Delta S_2^{0\#} \quad (9)$$

The enthalpy of activation ($\Delta H_2^{0\#}$) has been calculated with the help of the following equation¹³

$$\Delta H_2^{0\#} = \Delta\mu_2^{0\#} + T\Delta S_2^{0\#} \quad (10)$$

The free energies of activation of viscous flow $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ and $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$, per mole of solvent and solute, respectively have been obtained as per the above mentioned procedure. The values of $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ and $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ have been presented in Tables 4 and 5 respectively. It is seen that the values of $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ for mono- and disaccharides in water and also in (AN + water) mixed solvents are larger as compared to those of $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$, and that in each case ($\Delta\mu_2^{0\#} - \Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$) > 0. This shows that all the mono- and disaccharides behave as structure makers¹¹ in water as well as in (AN + water) mixed solvent systems. The values of entropy and enthalpy of activation of viscous flow at different temperatures have been calculated and presented in Table 6. It is seen that the values of $T\Delta S_2^{0\#}$ and $\Delta H_2^{0\#}$, are positive in water but negative in (AN + water) mixed solvent systems of different compositions. Further, it is seen that in the case of purely aqueous solutions, $\Delta H_2^{0\#} > T\Delta S_2^{0\#}$ thereby suggesting that solute-solvent interactions for the mono- and disaccharides are nearly complete in the ground state¹³. The positive values of $T\Delta S_2^{0\#}$ and $\Delta H_2^{0\#}$ in these solutions indicate that the formation of transition state is associated with bond breaking and a decrease in order and the slip-plane is somewhere in the region of centro-symmetric order. In mixed solvent systems, the negative values of $T\Delta S_2^{0\#}$ and $\Delta H_2^{0\#}$ suggest that the transition state is associated with bond making and an increase in order and that the slip-plane is in the disordered state¹⁴.

Experimental

Glucose, fructose, sucrose and maltose were of analytical reagents grade of 99.9% purity and were used as such. The reagents were always placed in a desiccator over P_2O_5 to keep them in dry atmosphere.

Freshly doubly distilled water (Sp. cond. $\sim 10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) was used for preparing the solutions of mono- and disaccharides in purely aqueous medium as well in (AN + water) mixed solvent systems of different compositions. An electronic balance (Mettler) having an accuracy of $1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ g}$ was used for the mass measurements.

Density was measured with the help of an apparatus similar to the one described by Ward and Millero and followed by Parmar *et al.*¹⁵. Viscosities of the solutions were measured at the desired temperature using an Ostwald's suspended level type viscometer¹⁶. Runs were repeated until three successive determinations were obtained within ± 0.1 s. Density and viscosity measurements were carried out in a thermostated bath, the temperature of which was maintained within ± 0.01 K of the required value.

References

- 1 R Gupta and M Singh, *J Indian Chem Soc*, 2004, **81**, 561, *J Chem Sci*, 2005, **117**, 275
- 2 D O Masson, *Phil Mag*, 1929, **8**, 218, G Jones and M Dole, *J Am Chem Soc*, 1929, **51**, 2950
- 3 F Franks, T R Ravenhill and D S Reid, *J Solution Chem*, 1972, **1**, 3
- 4 A Suggett, *J Solution Chem*, 1976, **5**, 33
- 5 M L Parmar and S Sharma, *J Indian Chem Soc*, 1990, **67**, 592
- 6 M L Parmar, R K Awasthi and M K Guleina, *J Chem Sci.*, 2004, **116**, 33
- 7 F J Millero, in "Structure and Transport Processes in Water and Aqueous Solutions", ed R A Horne, Wiley Interscience, New York, 1971, Ch 15, 622, *Chem Rev*, 1971, **71**, 147
- 8 H L Zhang, G H Chen and S J Hen, *J Chem Eng. Data*, 1997, **42**, 526
- 9 A Ben-Naim, "Water and Aqueous Solutions Introduction to a Molecular Theory", Plenum, New York, 1974, *J Chem Phys*, 1977, **67**, 4884, "Hydrophobic Interactions", Plenum, New York, 1980
- 10 M Zolkiewski, *J Solution Chem*, 1987, **16**, 1025
- 11 D Feakins, D J Freemantle and K G Lawrence, *J Chem Soc., Faraday Trans 1*, 1974, **70**, 795
- 12 S Glasstone, K Laidler and H Eyring, "The Theory of Rate Processes", McGraw Hill, New York, 1941
- 13 M L Parmar, D K Dhiman and R C Thakur, *Indian J Chem., Sect A*, 2002, **41**, 2032
- 14 R T M Bicknell, K G Lawrence, M A Seeley, D Feakins and L Werblan, *J Chem Soc., Faraday Trans 1*, 1976, **72**, 307
- 15 M L Parmar and D K Dhiman, *Indian J Chem., Sect A*, 2001, **40**, 1161, M L Parmar and S Sharma, *J Indian Chem Soc*, 1999, **76**, 202
- 16 A Findlay and J A Kitchner, "Practical Physical Chemistry", 8th ed., Longman, London, 1954